

THE ROLE OF LECTURER'S PERFORMANCE MODERATING ORGANIZATIONAL CLIMATE, MOTIVATION, AND LEADERSHIP ON EDUCATION QUALITY

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ABSTRACT

The destination study is for knowing the influence of direct and not direct Climate organization, and leadership To Quality education at the Private University of Bireuen City, North Aceh. Study this uses analysis quantitative with the determination sample Non-Probability Sampling amount sample 150. The data analysis used is SEM-PLS. Research results show that four Variable namely, Climate organization, leadership, motivation, and lecturer performance take effect direct positive and significant on Quality education, and lecturer performance could Moderate to two variables viz Leadership and Motivation to Quality education at the Private University of Bireuen City, North Aceh. Except for the Performance lecturer, no one could Moderate Climate organization to Quality education at the Private University of Bireuen City, North Aceh.

Keywords: Lecturer performance, climate organization, Leadership, Motivation, and Quality Education

1 INTRODUCTION

In something organization or education Source power, a man is a very holding role important for reach the destination organization. According to Bintoro and Daryanto (2017:15) stated the source power of a man is something knowledge or a method how to arrange relationships and roles to source the power owned by individuals in a manner efficient and effective as well as could use in a manner maximum so that achieved expected goals _ Education becomes something that needs to every human. Besides that existence education is one _ key base progress something nations and places in translating message constitution as well as means of building character and character something nation (Nurhakim 2021). level

education in Indonesia consists from education elementary, secondary, and education high. Higher education is a level of education that includes diploma, bachelor, master, doctoral, and professional programs as well as specialists organized in universities _ high (Ministry of Culture 2017). Existence college tall Becomes something institution preparing education _ participant to educate for Becomes member of the Public with academics, good character, and skills (Suryana 2018).

Table 1: Number of Universities in Aceh Province

College _	Status		Total
	Country	Private	
University	4	13	17
Institute	1	0	1
High School	0	38	38
Academy	0	33	33
Academy Community	1	0	1
Polytechnic	1	5	6

Source: PPDIKTI (2020) and LLDIKTI Region XIII (2022)

Aceh province is one _ of the provinces in Sumatra and the province this joined LLDIKTI Region XIII which regulates service education tall for the province. Based on PPDIKTI data (2020) there are 96 universities registered and active in the province of Aceh. As for the spread following The total number of universities in Aceh Province are 17 units with 4 state-owned units and 4 private ones as many as 13 units. Next, the total number of Institutes in Aceh Province is as many as 1 units and with state status. As for the total amount school, there are 38 units in total in Aceh Province status private. Next, the total amount there are as many academies in Aceh Province 33 units in total status private. The total number of academic communities in Aceh Province is as much as 1 unit and state status. Finally, the total number of polytechnics in Aceh Province is 6 units with 1 unit having state status and 1 unit being private. As many as 5 units. The whole college tall spread across the district and cities in Aceh province. But on research this only focus on one area only namely Bireuen City.

Table 1.3 Number of Universities in Bireuen City

College _	Status		Total
	Country	Private	
University	0	3	3
Institute	0	0	0
High School	0	0	0
Academy	0	1	1
Academy Community	0	0	0
Polytechnic	0	0	0

Source: LLDIKTI REGION XIII (2022)

Bireuen City is one _ District located in the province of Aceh. This city also exists college tall as much four universities and all of them are private with a distribution that is for in the form of 3 units of university (Al -Muslim University, University of Muhammadiyah Mahakarya Aceh, and the National Islamic University of Indonesia) and the form of an Academy of 1 unit (Munawarrah Midwifery Academy). The existence of these four universities expected could increase the quality of education in Bireuen City and Aceh Province. Quality good education _ will become a description that education in the region _ already good and growing.

Table 1.4 Number of Active Students and Lecturers in the City of Bireuen

College _	Amount	
	Student Active	Lecturer Active
Al-Muslim University	6761	290
University of Muhammadiyah Mahakarya Aceh	6198	275
Indonesian National Islamic University	4000	169
Academy Midwifery Munawarrah	56	9
Total	17015	733

Source: PPDIKTI (2022)

As previously stated that there are 4 tertiary institutions in the City of Bireuen and all of them are private. Based on PPDIKTI data (2022) from the four tertiary institutions in Bireuen City, the total number of active students is currently 17 015 people, and a total of 733 active lecturers. The distribution is for Al-Muslim University, the number of active students is 6761 people and the number of active lecturers is 290 people. At Muhammadiyah Mahakarya University in Aceh, the number of active students is 6198 people and the number of active lecturers is 275 people. Then, at the National Islamic University of Indonesia, the number of active students is 4,000 people and the number of active lecturers is 169 people. And finally, at the Munawarrah Midwifery Academy, there are 56 active students and 9 active lecturers.

Quality education is capable education _ that produces graduates who have the ability or competence good academic as well as non-academic and based on personal and social competencies, and values morals glorious, the whole is prowess capable of living and education produces someone who can practice faith, knowledge and practice good others (Suderadjat 2005). Because p the importance increase quality education something institutions especially colleges tall as spear end formal education. The increased quality of education expected could produce qualified and prepared graduates _ to socialize. Educators _ Becomes component important There are several factors in describing quality education among them leadership dean, motivation, and performance lecturer.

Dean as a leader inside _ something faculty has a role important for ensuring the implementation of learning and teaching processes with ok. The need for soul leadership from a dean will give influence big not only the sustainability of the learning process teach but also will take effect to quality of education from the faculty he leads

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Quality of Education

Mulyasa (2011) explains that Education quality includes the input, process, and output of Education. Educational Input referred to is something needed _ or required by Institutions/ Educational Institutions for the continuity of the educational process which includes source Educational resources, teaching process devices, as well vision and mission as well as a destination from the educational institution. The educational process in question is the

implementation process or continuity an Education and learning in something educational institutions /institutions that include starting planning, management of educational institutions and programs, learning processes, and monitoring up to Educational evaluation. Whereas intended educational output is the results obtained _ from the whole learning process in form performance school until produced graduates. _

According to Zahra (2014), the quality of education is the ability or competence of institution education in exploiting as well as manage sources of education, which is used to increase the ability of study participants to educate optimally maybe.

According to the Ministry of National Education (2003), the quality of education is not only could see from achievements _ _ but could compare with standard to set standards _ in Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System. The standard measurement of education quality in question is the Regulated National Education Standards in Regulation Government Number 57 of 2021. Standard national education is the minimum criteria for system education throughout the jurisdiction of the Unitary State Republic

Because of that Quality education plays a big role important for increasing the power competitive nation in accompanies everything _ sophisticated at the time this, because that Quality education is one _ priority in educating and nurturing students to achieve what to expect.

2.2. Lecturer Performance

Robbins (2001) states that performance is a measure of what is done and what is not done by employees. According to Nadeak (2020), lecturer performance is the output of the process carried out by lecturers through work presentations, work implementation, work achievement, work results, and work performance. Definition of performance other could refer to Supardi (2014) stating that teacher performance is a teacher's ability and success in doing work and the results achieved _ from profession the. The definition of performance too _ referenced from the Ministry of National Education (2005) which states that teacher performance is the ability for doing a profession or the tasks that the teacher has to complete something his job. Measurement of teacher performance is needed to determine quality education because teacher performance is an indicator of achievement destination education and learning.

According to Nadeak (2020) there are several employee performance indicators, namely: 1) Quality of work; 2) Punctuality; 3) Initiative; 4) Ability; and 5) Communication. Meanwhile, Supardi (2014) added that teacher performance is a teacher's ability and success in doing tasks learning indicated by the indicators including :

1. Planning learning, is activity plan, organizing, and designing learning starting from the activity initial, core activities and activities packed cover _ interesting possibilities for creating implementation quality learning. _
2. Procedure learning is the essence of activity learning plans that have made must hold in activity implementation learning. Regulation Minister No. 65 of 2013 mentions procedure

learning is the implementation of the RPP, including activity introduction, main body, and closing.

3. Evaluation of evaluation results learning is part of the learning process, that is evaluate with seeing the extent of the learning process that walks with kind and give follow carry on to results the.

2.3. Climate Organization

According to Wirawan (2007), Climate organization is defined as a perception of a member organization that can affect the attitude, behavior, and performance member organization that can determine performance organization. Whereas according to Lussier and Achua (2010) climate organizations can too define as quality influencing the internal environment of the organization behavior member organization. According to Davis and Newstrom (2000) enabling factors create climate conducive organization _ among others: 1) quality leadership; 2) trust ; 3) communication up and down; 4) feelings happy in work; 5) responsibility; 6) openness; 7) reasons enter sense for work hard; 8) opportunities; 9) reasons enter will for supervise bureaucracy; and 10) environment workers and participation. Meanwhile, according to Timpe, there are seven possible indicators _ referred for measuring climate organization, namely:

1. Connection Among superior underlying,
2. Openness communication.
3. Support and work the same active,
4. attention and appreciation,
5. Freedom argues and avoids criticism.
6. time for think, give time spare for think
7. Management and leadership style under control

2. 4. Leadership

Siagian (2010) explains that there are five roles of a leader namely 1) the Leader is a determinant direction aim organization to take a decision and push to realize the vision and mission carried out in a manner planned and gradual; 2) the Leader is a representative and interpreter talk organization in communicating with a party or other agencies ; 3) Leader is a communicator in conveying goals, strategies, actions, and decisions in operating operational activity; 4) Leader is an internal mediator complete possible conflict _ arise in the organization nor the environment; finally 5) Leader is a functioning integrator as unifier from various individuals and groups _ piker pattern towards destination together.

Whereas according to Mulyasa (2011) assessed a leader in the world of education has a role as that is:

1. Educators (educators), and leaders of educational institutions must always make an effort to increase quality learning by workers __ educators. Factor experience will greatly affect the professional leader. Educational Institutions must have the right strategy for empowering power education through cooperation or cooperative.
2. Administrators and leaders of Educational Institutions have close relationships _ with various activity management administrative nature _ recording, compiling, and documenting all programs of Institutions/ Institutions.
3. Supervisors and leaders of educational institutions supervise work done by power _ education. Supervision indeed could be carried out by the leader of the educational institution that plays the role of supervisor.
4. Leader (leader), the leader of the Educational Institution must be capable give guidance and supervision, improving willpower education, opening communication in two directions, and delegating tasks.
5. Innovators and leaders of Educational Institutions must have the right strategy for intertwining harmonious relationships _ with the neighborhood, and searching for new ideas.

2.5. Motivation

According to Umam (2012: 159). The definition of motivation covered various aspects of Acts or behavior man who can push somebody to behave or not behave. However, in the term following this motivation is encouragement man to act and behave. Meanwhile, according to Robbins (2010), motivation refers to the process by which effort somebody is energized, directed, and sustained going to achieve something purpose. Definition other discovered by Kreitner and Kinicki (2003) stated that motivation is a psychological process that arouses and directs behavior on achievement destination or goal-directed behavior.

According to Uno (2008) in measure, Internal motivation includes not quite enough he replied in doing a task, carrying out Duty with a clear target, having a destination clear and challenging, there is feedback on the results it works, happy at work, always spurred for more superior from others, and prioritize must achievement _ achieved moment work. Motivation external covers always attempting to Fulfill needs in life and work, being happy and praised on work, working with expected incentives, and working with expect noticed by friends and superiors.

2.7 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3 RESEARCH METHODS

Study this using approach quantitative. Data were obtained from a deployment questionnaire with a scale Likert with an amount sample of as many as 172 respondents. Research data were analyzed using structural equation model (SEM) analysis based on partial least squares (PLS). For testing influence direct and for measuring strength connection Among Variable independent with variable dependent. From variable research used.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Measurement Model Analysis (Outer Model)

Figure 2: Outer Model

Based on Figure 2 shows that the whole variable has Fulfill condition validity with the entire loading factor value indicator value > 0.7 . So could conduct testing next.

Construct Reliability Tests

Table 1: Results Construct Reliability Tests

Sampel 172, Var 5, Kuesioner 9,9,... *SAMPEL 172.splsm PLS Algorithm (Run No. 2)

Construct Reliability and Validity

Matrix	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance E
	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average ...
X1	0.892	0.893	0.914	0.571
X2	0.903	0.905	0.922	0.596
X3	0.908	0.909	0.924	0.577
Y	0.913	0.913	0.928	0.590
Z	0.935	0.935	0.944	0.605
Z.X1	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Z.X2	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Z.X3	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

The results of the analysis are shown in Table 1 above shows that the AVE value of each latent variable has a value > 0.5 and the value composite reliability and value of Cronbach's alpha every more latent variable of 0.7 then could conclude indicator variable capable of measure with ok.

Measurement Model Analysis (Inner Model)

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Table 2: R-Square

Sampel 172, Var 5, Kuesioner 9,9,... *SAMPEL 172.splsm

R Square

Matrix	R Square	R Square Adjusted
	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Y	0.964	0.963

Based on table 2 is known that the variable adjusted R-Square value performance employee of 0963 or 96.3% and the rest of 3.7% is influenced by other variables that are not researched in the study.

Predictive Relevance (Q²)

The value of Q2 has the same meaning as the coefficient R-Square determination. Big Q square value (Q2), 0 indicates the model has predictive relevance otherwise if a value (Q2) is less than this 0 shows the model has less predictive relevance in other words where all more Q2 value height, the model is considered could more suitable with data considerations Q2 value can conduct like following.

$$Q2 = 1 - (1 - R^2_1) (1 - R^2_2) \dots (R_n^2)$$

$$Q2 = 1 - (1 - 0.963)$$

$$Q2 = 1 - 0.037$$

$$Q2 = 0.963$$

Based on the results the Q2 value of 0.963 so could be concluded that the variable in the study this Lecturer performance, climate organization, Leadership, Motivation, and Quality education give authenticity data contribution in the existing structural model by 96.3%, then the remaining 0.037% is necessary developed besides from variable study this.

Effect Size (F2)

Effect size (F2) determines the godness of the model. Also to find out whether the predictor variable has a weak influence, sufficient or strong influence at the structural level.

Hypothesis Test

Table 3: Influence Direct

	Original ...	Sample ...	Standard ...	T Statistic...	P Values
X1 -> Y	0.254	0.262	0.052	4.872	0.000
X2 -> Y	0.163	0.169	0.046	3.518	0.000
X3 -> Y	0.349	0.351	0.044	7.930	0.000
Z -> Y	0.214	0.198	0.067	3.167	0.002
Z.X1 -> Y	-0.052	-0.051	0.044	1.193	0.234
Z.X2 -> Y	0.103	0.099	0.035	2.986	0.003
Z.X3 -> Y	-0.078	-0.075	0.039	1.986	0.048

From Table 3 above can be seen that there is influence and no influence from:

1. Climate Effects Organization to Education Quality _ direct

Climate organizations take to affect positive and significant Education Quality. this result is seen from a score significance of 0.000 small than 0.05. This means the increase in Climate Organization so will the more increase significant the Quality of Education at the Private University of Bireuen City –North Aceh. Research results in this are in line with results research that conducted by Research

2. Leadership to Quality of Education indirect

Leadership takes effect significantly and is significant to Education Quality. Is known score significance Leadership of 0.000 more small than 0.05. This means if a leader operates his job with maximum, the lecturers work with good so more increase the quality of education by what is expected. this result is to the results of Research conducted by Sarnoto _ et al . (2019) found that the leadership chairman study program takes effect quality study program education management Islamic education at STAI Darunnajah Jakarta. This show that the important role leader in something institution Becomes spear main in ensure quality education from institution education especially in college tall in line with research conducted by Rabukit _ Damanik (2019) that Leadership takes an effect significant positive to quality education, in line with what is being done research by H. Hodyat (2016) that leadership increase quality education.

3. Influence Motivation to Quality education kindly direct

Motivation takes effect on Quality education. This is seen from P Values of more than 0,000 small from 0.05. This means Motivation increase Education Quality will increase this research by Suratni _ et al. (2015) found that motivation takes effect the enhancement of quality education at the Faculty of Technology IPB Agriculture in line with research conducted by Siti Zubaidah (2015 Motivation influential teacher work positively on quality education.

4. Effect of Lecturer Performance on Quality education kindly direct

Lecturer Performance takes an effect on Quality education. This is seen from P Values of more than 0.002 small from 0.05. This means Motivation increase Education Quality will increase this research by Suratni _ et al. (2015) found that motivation takes effect enhancement of quality education at the Faculty of Technology IPB Agriculture in line with research conducted by Nurhakim (2021) and Sopandi (2019) found that performance takes effect to quality education in one institution education

5. Lecturer Performance no could Moderate Among Climate organization to This Education Quality look where P. Values of 0.234 more big of this 0.05 show that Climate Organization is not significant to the Quality of Education at the Private University of Bireuen City, North Aceh contrary to research that was carried out by Nurhakim (2021), Rahman et al. (2020), and Sopandi (2019) found that performance takes effect to quality education in one institution education.

6. Lecturer Performance could Moderate Among Leadership to This Education Quality look where P. Values of 0.003 more small this 0.05 show that Leadership is significant to the Quality of Education at Private Universities in Bireuen City, North Aceh p by research conducted by Kusdiby (2021) states that leaders as holder policy and power have a role in the effort to

enhancement quality education in college high and this no regardless from Lecturer Performance. This is also in line with research conducted by Yusran Razak et al (2016) Leadership in college tall have a role important in managing college high-quality _ performance good lecturer, Represents _ evaluation of quality or quality education in college high.

7. Lecturer Performance could Moderate Among Motivation to This Education Quality look where P. Values of 0.048 more small than 0.05 at this private university in the city of Bireuen, North Aceh in line with research conducted by Suprianto (2011) that Competence lecturer takes effect significant quality service to student motivation to teach take effect significant quality service to student competent lecturer could influence motivation lecturer to quality service student Sopandi (2019) found that performance takes effect to quality education in one institution education and this because it is driven by strong motivation.

5. CONCLUSION

Research conclusions obtained _ that in a manner direct variable Lecturer performance, climate Organization, Leadership, and Motivation take effect significant to Quality education at the Private University of Bireuen City – North Aceh and Lecturer Performance could Moderate two variables viz Leadership and Motivation to Quality education, except lecturer performance no could moderate Climate organization to Quality education at the Private University of Bireuen City – North Aceh.

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